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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE INITIAL RECOGNITION OF LEASE OBLIGATIONS

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqot ijara munosabatlari ishtirokchilari o'rtasida yuzaga keladigan majburiyatlarni tan olishning tashkiliy asoslarini va uni rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq xalqaro tajribani o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ijara majburiyati, diskontlash stavkasi, ijara to'lovlari, aktivdan foydalanish huquqi, ijara muddati, ijara majburiyati amortizatsiyasi.*

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании рассматриваются организационные основы признания обязательств, возникающих между участниками отношений аренды, и международный опыт, связанный с его развитием.*

Ключевые слова: *Обязательство по аренде, ставка дисконтирования, арендные платежи, право пользования активом, срок аренды, амортизация обязательства по аренде.*

Abstract. *This study examines the organizational foundations of the recognition of obligations arising between the participants of rental relations and the international experience related to its development.*

Key words: *Lease liability, discount factor, lease payments, right-of-use assets, lease term, lease liability amortization.*

Tenancy has existed since the beginning of human culture. Initially, they had to temporarily use the property belonging to others, i.e. work and labor tools, for a fee. With the development of social relations, the use of another person's property for a temporary fee has developed, and the practice of using rent in the implementation of the activities of enterprises in the economy has developed. In this case, the practice of enterprises using necessary investments for their activities, i.e. constructions, industrial equipment and natural resources for rent, was formed. As a result, the scale of lease relations in the economy has increased, and the need to clearly define the duties and obligations of the parties entering into lease relations has arisen. To date, many researchers have conducted research and given different definitions regarding the

definition and determination of lease obligations. Researchers in their scientific research and scientific literature generally define the obligation of rent as follows:

A lease obligation is a financial obligation arising from a lease agreement between a lessee and another party, usually a lessor, in which the enterprise receives the right to use the asset for a certain period of time and makes periodic lease payments in return⁶.

According to IFRS 16 (IFRS 16)-Lease standard, a lease obligation is any obligation recognized in proportion to the right-of-use asset that should be recorded in the lessee’s balance sheet, and in accordance with the standard’s requirements, the lease agreement is included in the financial statements of the enterprise. is used to correctly reflect the financial impact on the situation⁷.

According to IFRS 16, when recognizing the lease obligation, first of all, it is necessary to collect information related to the recognition of the lease obligation. After making sure that all the information is accurate and complete, the rental obligation can be calculated.

Let’s take a step-by-step look at how to record a lease liability.

In order to take into account the lease liability in the accounting balance, three factors must be determined first (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factors to determine lease obligation.

This information is needed to calculate the rental obligation. Let’s see how to put it all together.

⁶ <https://www.genio.ac/glossary/lease-liability>

⁷ <https://www.bdo.global/getmedia/4b4c5f48-af18-4caa-b598-630ba9b937cf/IFRS-16-In-Practice-2023-2024.pdf?ext=.pdf>

Lease term. Calculating the lease liability begins with determining the term of the lease, which includes the non-cancelable term of the lease and additional terms if the lessee and lessor have the option to extend or cancel the lease. The lease term is important because it determines the period over which the lease liability is amortized⁸.

Rental payments. Rental fees include the fees specified in the rental agreement. Some payments may be subject to certain conditions. For example, if the lease agreement contains options for renewing or terminating the lease, it will include fees associated with them. Such payments are variable, but due to their nature or condition they are inevitable and are therefore "essentially fixed rents".

Discount rate. When calculating the lease liability, the lessee must determine a discount rate to estimate the fair value of future lease payments at the recognition date. It uses the borrowing rate that the lessee could borrow to purchase the same asset on similar terms for a period comparable to the lease term. The discount rate should take into account factors such as the lessee's creditworthiness, the principal collateral value of the asset, and prevailing interest rates at the lease inception date. The discount rate is used to calculate the present value of future lease payments under the lease using the lessee's best estimate.

After collecting the necessary information (ie, lease term, lease payment, and discount rate), the fair value of future payments over the lease term should be determined using the discount rate. This value is reflected in accounting as a lease liability.

To better understand the calculation of the rent obligation, let's consider the following situation. We assume that the following information is available regarding the rental obligation:

- Lease term: 4 years and it is not possible to extend this term;
- The rent is 40,000,000 soums per year and is paid at the end of each year;
- The discount rate is 12% (borrowing rate). The following formula is used to determine the discounting factor⁹:

$$\frac{1}{(1+r)^n}$$

r -borrowing rate;

n is the number of cycles.

To determine the rental obligation, a schedule of rent payments is prepared based on the rental period (Table 1).

⁸ <https://tax.thomsonreuters.com/blog/how-to-record-the-lease-liability-and-corresponding-asset>

⁹ <https://www.accaglobal.com/gb/en/student/exam-support-resources/fundamentals-exams-study-resources/f7/technical-articles/ifrs16.html>

Table 1 (in soum)

Indicators	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Expected rent payments	40 000 000	40 000 000	40 000 000	40 000 000
Discount rate	12%			

After that, the future rent payments are discounted using the discount rate and the factor determined based on the relevant period in the following order (Table 2).

Table 2 (in soum)

Period	Rental payments	Discount rate	Present value
1	40 000 000	$1/(1+0.12)^1$	35 714 286
2	40 000 000	$1/(1+0.12)^2$	31 887 755
3	40 000 000	$1/(1+0.12)^3$	28 471 210
4	40 000 000	$1/(1+0.12)^4$	25 420 723
Total present value of liabilities			121 493 974

The sum of the present values of future lease payments is recognized as a lease liability. It can be seen from the table that the initial value of the lease obligation was 121,493,974 soums.

For the initial recognition of the lease obligation, the following transfer is made in the accounting of the enterprise:

Dr The right to use the asset is 121,493,974 soums

Cr Lease obligation 121,493,974 soums

The procedure for determining and recognizing the rental obligation considered above is determined by the rules of IFRS 16.

From the above, we can see that in international practice, the recognition of lease obligations is carried out in accordance with IFRS 16, and accounting and reporting are carried out in a more systematic and orderly manner. This ensures accurate and reliable information for information users.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, accounting for lease relations and transactions related to them is approved by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Lease", Order No. 54 of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 11.05.2009 Regulation "On the procedure for reflecting lease transactions in accounting", No. 6 "Lease accounting" and No. 21 "Accounting plan of financial and economic activities of economic entities and its application" is regulated and recognized by BHMS named "instructions on"¹⁰.

¹⁰ <https://lex.uz/docs/-112328>

According to the above regulatory documents, rent in Uzbekistan is considered separately into financial and operational rent. The procedure for recognizing the lease obligation differs according to the type of lease. In this case, lease obligations are recognized at the beginning of the lease term under a financial lease. In case of operating leases, the lease obligations are recognized proportionally to the completed lease periods.

According to the operating lease agreement, after the end of the relevant period, the following accounting transfer is issued for the recognition of the obligation:

Dr Rent expense (2000, 2100, 2300, 2500, 2600, 2700, 9400 and other accounts depending on the purpose of fixed assets received under the operating lease agreement)

Cr Lease payable

It can be seen from this that in the practice of Uzbekistan, obligations under operational lease are recognized in the monthly amount of rent payment from the end of the relevant month. That is, the actual value of the total payments expected under the lease agreement is not estimated at the beginning of the lease agreement. As a result, obligations related to lease relationships are not fully reflected in financial reports.

It is important that businesses provide accurate information about their rental obligations. Because information about obligations is one of the important indicators for the investors and creditors, who are the main users of financial statements, when making decisions about the enterprise. Accurate accounting of lease obligations and reliable disclosure of information about them in financial statements directly affects the decisions made by users.

In summary, the lease liability is the obligation arising from the lease of the asset and represents the initial value of the future lease payments that the enterprise must make and plays an important role in accurately reflecting the financial position of the enterprise. For this reason, the improvement of the norms of the national legislation on lease accounting based on the rules of IFRS 16 is one of the urgent tasks today.

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